

CONDENSATION OF ALDEHYDES WITH MALONIC ACID. PART XX.
CONDENSATION OF 3-NITRO-2-HYDROXYBENZALDEHYDE

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3-Nitro-2-hydroxybenzaldehyde (3-nitrosalicylaldehyde) is condensed with malonic acid under different conditions. As in the case of the 5-nitro-2-hydroxybenzaldehyde (Part XVIII) there appears to be no condensation in the absence of any condensing agent or in the presence of glacial acetic acid. In the presence of pyridine, piperidine or a mixture of the two, 3-nitro-2-hydroxybenzylidene (i. e. 3-nitrosalicylidene)-malonic acid is obtained in varying amounts, the highest yield so far obtained being 53%.

This condensation is very much in line with that of 5-nitrosalicylaldehyde under identical conditions. The three peculiarities noted in the earlier paper are found in this condensation also, viz., there is no condensation in the presence of glacial acetic acid or in the absence of any condensing agent, the aldehyde being almost entirely recovered unchanged; in the presence of the bases 3-nitrosalicylidene-malonic acid is obtained, analogous to the 5-nitro product; and the dibasic acid has not been converted, so far, into the corresponding mono-acid by decarboxylation on heating.

The identity of 3-nitrosalicylidene-malonic acid is established by the analytical data; it appears that a nitro or a bromo group adds to the ease of formation and the stability of salicylidene-malonic acid.

The highest yield is 53%, very much below the highest yield obtained of the 5-nitrosalicylidene-malonic acid (part XVIII, *loc. cit.*).

EXPERIMENTAL

The 3-nitrosalicylaldehyde was obtained together with the 5-nitrosalicylaldehyde as described in Part XVIII (Pandya, Saxena and Tinku, *this issue*, p. 443).

Miller and Kinkelin (*Ber.*, 1887, 20, 1931) have condensed 3-nitrosalicylaldehyde by Perkin's method, and obtained 8-nitrocoumarin thereby. On repeating the experiment, however, nothing was obtained. So also Stuart's method (*J. Chem. Soc.*, 1883, 83, 142) i. e. heating on the water-bath 3-nitrosalicylaldehyde with malonic acid in the presence of glacial acetic acid, gave no product, nor was any product isolated when the aldehyde and malonic acid were heated alone together for 12 hours, once on a water-bath and a second time at a higher temperature rising up to 130°.

With Pyridine.—Heating the aldehyde and malonic acid with traces of pyridine (0.2 mol.) produced different yields of a certain acid, according to the conditions of heating. Thus 6 hours' heating, either on the water-bath or at 100-105°, produced practically the same yield, viz. 21.1% and 22.2% respectively. (Some aldehyde was recovered unchanged: if this were subtracted, the yield would be greater.) The product was identical, m. p. 182°. The same product was obtained by the other method described below.

With an alteration in the heating, the yield increased. Thus heating at 100-105° or at 98° for 10 hours (in different experiments) gave very nearly the same yield, about 48-49%.

With 1 mol. of pyridine (i.e., 1:1:1 mol.), and heating on a water-bath for 12 hours, the product obtained was 49.3%.

With excess of pyridine (2 mols. and 3 mols.) and heating (water-bath) for 12 hours, the yield was only slightly higher, viz. 52.2%.

With Piperidine.—With a molecule of piperidine, and heating on a water-bath for 12 hours, the yield was 41.6%.

With pyridine-piperidine mixture (Robinson's method, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1925, 1977). the yield was about 53%.

Vorsatz's method (*J. prakt. Chem.*, 1936, 145, 265) of room temperature condensation with excess of pyridine, gave in 3 weeks, 21.7% yield.

Kept alone in ether solution, without any condensing agent, for three weeks at room-temperature, it failed to give any product.

The acid product was yellow in colour, melting with effervescence at 182°. It was readily soluble in ether, acetone, alcohol and glacial acetic acid; slightly soluble in benzene, ethyl acetate and cold water; almost insoluble in ether and chloroform; also somewhat soluble in hot water.

The acid gave a deep red colour with concentrated sulphuric acid. It also gave a deep red colour with alcoholic ferric chloride solution; it decolorised Baeyer's reagent, and the solid acid or its solution in glacial acetic acid decolorised bromine readily in the cold. [Found: N, 5.48, 5.68; M. W. (Rast), 258.1; M. W. (Ag. salt), 257.4; equiv. (by titration), 118.4. C₁₀H₆O₄N (3-nitrosalicylidene-malonic acid) requires N, 5.53%; M. W., 253.3; equiv., 126.5].

Production of colour in the titration, as well as in the camphor in Rast's method, was responsible for greater deviations from the theoretical than is usual.

Experiments to obtain the corresponding monobasic acid by heating the dibasic acid gave an acid melting at about at 151° (O. S. S.); this has still to be investigated.